

Influence of deposition parameters on the building rate, in-situ formation of austenite and tensile properties of SAF 2507 SDSS fabricated by directed energy deposition

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Abstract

Industry applications of duplex stainless steels require a two-phase microstructure with a nearly balanced austenite-ferrite content to achieve good mechanical properties and good corrosion resistance. The most widespread additive manufacturing methods such as selective laser melting or laser powder bed fusion, provide nearly fully ferritic microstructures due to the very high cooling rate, and the post-processing heat treatment must be performed. In contrast, other additive manufacturing methods, such as directed deposition methods, reach lower cooling rates and enable to obtain an equal ferrite-austenite ratio directly in the microstructure of the as-built state. In this work, the super duplex stainless steel SAF 2507 was deposited by directed energy deposition. The process parameters, namely, the laser power, laser beam spot, and powder feed rate, were varied to investigate the impact of the energy area density on the microstructure and tensile properties. A decrease in the energy area density caused an increase in the austenite content of 48 vol.% and a numerical simulation of the sample temperature distribution inside the block during deposition, explaining the relationship between the amount of in situ formed austenite and the deposition parameters, was provided. Simultaneously, the deposition rate increased by more than five times. In contrast, the samples deposited at a higher building rate are characterized by greater porosity and lower elongation values in the vertical direction. The effect of the deposition parameters on the yield strength is low.

Keywords

Super Duplex Stainless Steel, Microstructure, Tensile properties, Additive manufacturing, Directed Energy Deposition, Laser power

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing technologies have undergone great development in the last decade. A wide range of materials have started to be additively manufactured. Among metallic materials, various types of steel including duplex stainless steels (DSSs) [1–3], titanium [4,5], nickel [6], aluminium [7], and other alloys, such as functionally graded and multi-materials [8,9], have been prepared by additive manufacturing methods. In the case of DSSs, there are three main additive manufacturing methods – powder bed fusion [1,10,11], directed energy deposition (DED) [2,12,13] and wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) [14]. DSSs generally have good

properties such as high strength, good corrosion resistance, formability and weldability, and are therefore widely often used in the chemical industry; power plants; and marine, gas and oil applications [15]. However, in order to achieve these properties, the microstructure of DSSs must consist of a balanced ferrite-austenite ratio (austenite provides high toughness, ductility, good formability, improves the general corrosion resistance, including pitting and crevice corrosion while ferrite provides high strength, improves weldability and is less susceptible to stress corrosion cracking, particularly in chloride environments), and undesirable secondary phases such as carbides, nitrides, and intermetallic compounds must be absent in the microstructure. Otherwise, the mechanical properties, especially toughness and corrosion resistance will be radically degraded [16–18]. Therefore, a heat treatment, called solution annealing, is usually applied to obtain a balanced 50/50 ferrite-austenite mixture in the microstructure without secondary phases, good mechanical properties or high corrosion resistance. Thus, solution annealing (SA) is usually carried out above 1000 °C, followed by rapid cooling [19,20], in commercial wrought material. On the other hand, in the case of duplex stainless steels fabricated by additive manufacturing methods, there is an opportunity to modify the deposition parameters to obtain the balanced phase composition and desired properties immediately in the as-built state without the need for post-manufacturing heat treatment.

Powder bed additive manufacturing are the most widespread laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) are often used for the fabrication of DSSs. The process begins with a thin layer of powdered material being spread evenly across a build platform. A high-energy source, such as a laser or electron beam, then selectively melts or sinters the powder according to the design specifications for that layer. After each layer is fused, the build platform is lowered by a fraction of the powder layer's thickness. A new layer of powdered material is spread over the previously fused layer. This process is repeated layer by layer until the entire set of objects is built up. DSSs deposited by this method usually exhibit nearly fully ferrite microstructures [1,10,11,21–24]. The formation of austenite is limited due to the very high cooling rate during deposition, which is also responsible for the preferential orientation of grains along the building direction and high dislocation density. This results in the high strength of the as-built state. Heat treatment, specifically solution annealing (SA) is required to achieve a balanced austenite-ferrite microstructure. A decrease in strength and an increase in plastic properties occur during solution annealing as well [1,11,20,21,24,25].

In contrast, additive manufacturing methods such as directed energy deposition (DED) [2,12,13,26] and wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) [27] can deposit DSSs with a higher austenite content in the as-built state compared to powder bed methods. WAAM methods involve the deposition of a material using an electric arc and a continuous wire feed. The wire is melted by the arc and deposited layer by layer to build up a three-dimensional structure. It offers the advantage of producing large and complex parts with high precision. In the as-built state, the austenite content reaches more than 70 vol. % [28]. As in welded joints and as-built microstructures prepared by direct deposition of DSSs, there are three forms of austenite (IGA – Intragranular austenite, GBA – Grain boundary austenite, and WA – Widmanstätten austenite) [29]. DED methods are very suitable for repairing or adding additional material to existing components or depositing functionally graded materials (FGMs). Powder is deposited layer by layer from the nozzle onto the surface of the component. The as-built microstructure consists of an austenite-ferrite mixture. The ratio of austenite to ferrite in the microstructure can be balanced. The austenite content depends on deposition parameters such as the laser power, temperature of the platform, and platform preheating. Some works [12,13] reported a near balanced austenite-ferrite ratio in an as-built microstructure. Other studies [26,30] presented results with a lower fraction of austenite in the as-built microstructure (between 20 and

40%) and highlight the possibility of pore formation in the microstructure and construction irregularities when varying the parameters of the DED process. The cooling rate is considered a crucial factor influencing the austenite fraction in the microstructure of as-built samples produced by various additive manufacturing methods. A high cooling rate (10^5 - 10^6 K/s) in LPBF suppresses the formation of austenite [13,31,32]. Directed deposition methods (DED and WAAM) exhibit lower cooling rates (10^2 - 10^3 K/s) [13,33–36], leading to higher austenite content in the as-built state.

According to the literature, previous works investigating DSSs and SDSSs additively manufactured by DED method compared the properties of these steels deposited by DED with commercial wrought and forged material [2,12,13,30], followed the dependence of austenite content on the distance from substrate, and compared numerical simulations of solid state reaction with experimental observations [12,37,38] or studied the influence of deposition parameters such as laser scanning speed, beam diameter, powder feed rate while laser power is constant [13]; laser power and scanning speed while powder flow rate is constant [30]; and laser power while other deposition parameters are constant [37]. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work investigating the influence of DED parameters such as laser power, beam diameter, layer thickness, hatch distance and powder feed rate (while laser scanning is constant) on properties of the SAF2507 SDSS. Three different deposition conditions with an increasing building rate and a decreasing energy area density (EAD) were used and the impact on microstructure (mainly focused on austenite content) and tensile properties were evaluated. Additionally, the numerical simulation of temperature distribution inside the deposited cube was calculated to evaluate the influence of laser power on the cooling rate.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Material preparation

In this study, commercial nitrogen-atomized super duplex stainless steel SAF2507 (UNS 32750) powder produced by Sandvik Osprey Ltd was used. The chemical composition of SAF 2507 steel and the supplied SAF2507 powder are presented in **Tab. 1**. The powder particles were spherical or elongated in shape and the particle size ranged from 45 μm to 150 μm . The actual chemical compositions of the deposited cubes were measured by a Q4 Tasman optical emission spectrometer (Bruker Elemental GmbH, Kalkar, Germany) and nitrogen content using a gas analyser Galileo G8 (Bruker Elemental GmbH, Kalkar, Germany).

Tab. 1 The nominal chemical compositions of SAF 2507 steel, the supplied powder, and the chemical composition of the deposited cubes in weight percent (wt.%).

Elements (wt.%)	C	Si	Mn	Cr	Mo	Ni	N	Fe
SAF2507	<0.03	<0.70	<2.00	24.0-26.0	3.0-4.0	6.0-8.0	0.20-0.30	Bal.
Powder	0.02	0.4	0.9	24.8	4.0	6.9	0.3	Bal.
SDM800	0.023	0.5	0.9	24.9	3.9	6.9	0.27	Bal.
SDM1600	0.024	0.4	0.8	24.8	3.9	6.8	0.29	Bal.
SDM2400	0.022	0.4	0.8	24.8	3.9	6.8	0.30	Bal.

The experimental blocks were fabricated under an argon 5.0 (99.999%) protective atmosphere using the INSSSTEK MX-600 system (InssTek, Daejeon, Korea) equipped with a 2 kW Yttrium fibre infrared laser (wavelength of 1070 nm). The dimensions of the blocks were 20 \times 20 \times 20 mm. Direct metal tooling (DMT) was applied during the deposition process. In DMT mode, the deposition process is controlled to maintain a constant layer height, ensured

by adjusting the laser power. Optical sensors are used to maintain the ideal distance of 9 mm from the melt pool to the nozzle. The ZigZag deposition strategy with 90° rotation of individual layers, as described in [26], was used with the SDM800, SDM1600, and SDM2400 modules. The deposition parameters for the individual modules are summarized in **Tab. 2**.

Tab. 2 Process parameters of DED for individual modules.

Module	SDM800	SDM1600	SDM2400
Laser power (W)	~500	~950	~1300
Laser scanning speed (mm/min)	849	849	849
Beam diameter (μm)	800	1600	2400
Layer thickness (μm)	250	600	900
Hatch distance (μm)	500	1100	1500
Powder feed rate (g/min)	3.5	5.6	10.0
Gas flow (l/min)	15	23	33
Deposition time (min)	101	34	22

2.2 Microstructural analysis

For metallographic observations, the specimens were cut parallel to the building direction, ground with SiC grinding papers and polished with a final step of 0.05 μm OPS suspension. The microstructure was observed using a NIKON Eclipse MA 200 optical microscope and a JEOL IT 500 HR scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an EDS analyser Octane Elite Super for the determination of the chemical composition of austenite and ferrite. The grain size (GS), grain orientation spread (GOS), and geometrically necessary dislocation parameters were analysed from the acquired EBSD data using a TSL OIM8 software. The EBSD data were collected under the following conditions: acceleration voltage of 20 kV, an area of 806 × 900 μm, a step size of 1 μm, and a tilt angle of 70°.

The phase composition was characterized using a Bruker D8 Discover diffractometer (Bruker AXS GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) with a copper anode ($\lambda_{K\alpha 1} = 0.15406$ nm). XRD data were collected five times at different regions with polycapillary X-ray optics (2 mm in diameter). The phase composition and lattice parameters were evaluated by the Rietveld refinement [39] method using Topas software.

2.3 Tensile properties

The tensile properties of the deposited SDSS were evaluated via miniaturized tensile tests (MTTs). Six MTT specimens were extracted from each deposited block. Tensile testing was performed at ambient temperature using an electromechanical test machine TiraTest with a 10 kN load cell. The strain was measured by a contactless Mercury RT system based on digital image correlation calibrated in 2D mode with one camera. A black–white contrast pattern was prepared on the specimen surface to track the deformation. The initial extensometer length of 4 mm was applied based on the initial cross-sectional dimensions of the proportional tensile specimens. Specimens were tested at a cross-head velocity of 0.25 mm/min, which corresponds to a strain rate of 0.00025 /s. The tensile specimen had a flat shape, with a gauge length of 4.5 mm, a width of 1 mm and a thickness of 5 mm. The testing procedure followed the ISO 6892–1/ASTM E8 standard.

2.4 Numerical simulation

The temperature model of the DED process was created in Simufact Welding version 2024.1. The model was created from hexa elements. The substrate consisted of 1750 elements with an edge size of 4mm. The deposited layer contained 16484, 3440 and 1832 elements for SDM800, SDM1600 and SDM2400 respectively. The height of the elements was chosen to represent the height of the deposited layer (0.25, 0.6 and 0.9mm for SDM800, SDM1600 and SDM2400 respectively). G-codes representing the motion instructions of the DED process were imported into the simulation software. An example of the model layout is shown in the **Fig. 1a**. The thermal material properties of SAF2507 and the substrate were generated based on the chemical composition in JMatPro. The heat transfer coefficient (HTC) was determined by comparing the measured **Fig. 1b** and calculated temperatures for the SDM1600.

Fig. 1 a) FEM model of the SDM1600 and b) example of temperature distribution for SDM1600 during the deposition process.

An Advanced Thermal Cycle (ATC) method was used for the computation. The principle of ATC is to combine several computational steps into one and thus reduce the computational time.

3 Results

3.1 Effect on the microstructure and phase composition

The crucial role of utility properties such as strength, toughness, and corrosion resistance depends on the chemical composition and phase distribution in the microstructure. Thus, the chemical compositions of all the deposited cubes were determined to exclude undesirable changes in chemical composition during deposition. The results of chemical composition measurements are presented in **Tab. 1**. The laser power did not affect the chemical composition, and evaporation of the alloying elements did not occur during deposition.

The phase fraction analysis via XRD revealed an increase in the austenite content from 28 vol.% to 48 vol.% with increasing laser power; see the XRD patterns in **Fig. 2**. No σ -phase or other undesirable phases were detected by XRD analysis. A small change in the lattice parameters of austenite and ferrite occurred during the deposition under different laser powers. Generally, the lattice parameters of ferrite increased, whereas the lattice parameters of austenite decreased with increasing laser power (**Tab. 2**).

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of the SDM800, SDM1600 and SDM2400 samples deposited under different conditions.

Tab. 3 Austenite contents, lattice parameters and porosities of the SDM800, SDM1600 and SDM2400 samples.

Sample	Austenite content (vol.%)	Austenite a (Å)	Ferrite a (Å)	Porosity (%)
SDM800	28 ± 3	3.6243 ± 0.0007	2.8801 ± 0.0007	<0.01
SDM1600	40 ± 3	3.6215 ± 0.0006	2.8810 ± 0.0006	0.03
SDM2400	48 ± 2	3.6219 ± 0.0005	2.8831 ± 0.0007	0.2

In addition to phase composition, various deposition parameters influenced the porosity and size of the melt pool. The porosity rose with increasing laser beam diameter from 800 μm to 2400 μm, as **Tab. 3** summarized. The dimensions of the melt pool also increased. The average width (w) of the melt pool increased from 496 μm to 1151 μm to 1644 μm, and the depth (d) of the melt pool increased from 236 μm to 711 μm to 919 μm for the individual deposition parameters SDM800, SDM1600 and SDM2400, as shown in the light micrographs in **Fig. 3**. LM micrographs also revealed differences in the distribution of IGA in the samples. In the SDM800 sample, IGA precipitated predominantly along the boundaries of the melt pool, probably due to reheating during the deposition of upper layers [26], while inside the melt pool, only GBA was found, which formed along the boundaries of ferritic grains. In the case of the SDM1600 sample, the region without IGA significantly decreased, and in the SDM2400 sample, the austenite was uniformly distributed throughout the microstructure. Additionally, the boundaries of individual melt pools are less discernible in the SDM2400 sample. In all the samples, large columnar grains of ferrite are consistently observed inside the melt pool, and are oriented in the direction of heat dissipation, with smaller ferritic grains located beneath the lower edge of the melt pool. The IGA particles precipitated in these smaller ferritic grains observed by SEM are shown in **Fig. 3**. The SEM images also revealed the presence of oxide particles in the microstructure of all the samples, which was also described in previous works [2,13,26].

Fig. 3 LM and SEM micrographs showing differences in melt pool's dimensions and austenite distribution in the microstructure of a) SDM800, b) SDM1600 and c) SDM2400 samples. SEM micrographs (right) were taken in the region rich in IGA beneath the lower edge of the melt pool.

The EBSD analysis confirmed the XRD and LM results (**Fig. 4**). By the use of a smaller laser beam, austenite was formed mainly as grain boundary austenite (GBA). While the IGA was formed only close to the melt pool

boundaries with the SDM800 module, the increasing laser power caused uniform precipitation of the IGA in the microstructure. Generally, the area fraction of austenite increased with increasing laser beam diameter for not only IGA but also GBA and WA. The coarsening of austenite occurred with a larger laser beam spot, as demonstrated in **Tab. 4**. A greater number of austenite grains divided the ferrite grains into smaller grains. Thus, the grain size of ferrite deposited with the SDM800 module is twice as large as that of ferrite grains deposited with the SDM2400 module.

Fig. 4 EBSD phase and GOS maps with colour distribution of recrystallized (blue colour), transition grains (yellow colour) and non-recrystallized grains (red colour) of a) SDM800, b) SDM1600 and c) SDM2400 samples.

Generally, the recrystallized material is free from deformation and distortion between grains and has a low GOS value [40,41]. Thus, GOS maps were collected to evaluate the effect of laser power on the distortions between

grains. The following threshold values were used for the comparison of the investigated samples. The recrystallized grains reached GOS values up to 1.5. The grains with GOS parameters between 1.5 and 3.0 were considered transient grains, and the grains with GOS parameters above 3.0 corresponded to non-recrystallized grains. The significantly largest fraction of recrystallized grains was found in the SDM2400 sample. With the use of a lower laser energy, more transient and non-recrystallized grains were detected. A comparison of the GOS parameters between austenite and ferrite is interesting. For the SDM2400 sample, the recrystallized grains of ferrite accounted for approximately 98 % of the total ferrite, while the recrystallized fraction of austenite was 69%. Equal fractions (approximately 58% and 60%) of austenite and ferrite recrystallized grains were found in the SDM1600 sample, and in the SDM800 sample, the recrystallized austenite grains had similar values of about 54%, but the recrystallized ferrite created an area fraction of only 18%.

Tab. 4 EBSD results summary: fraction area of austenite, grain size of austenite and ferrite and recrystallized, transient and non-recrystallized grains fractions.

Sample	Austenite fraction (%)	Austenite GS (μm)	Ferrite GS (μm)	GOS Austenite (%)			GOS Ferrite (%)		
				0-1.5	1.501-3	3-100	0-1.5	1.501-3	3-100
SDM800 [26]	19.1	2.4	11.2	54.0	29.4	16.6	18.9	76.2	4.9
SDM1600	35.2	3.3	9.0	57.9	32.1	10.0	60.2	38.2	1.6
SDM2400	48.0	3.7	5.5	68.8	24.4	6.8	97.6	2.2	0.2

The dislocation density value, which represented the number of defects in the crystal lattice, was assessed based on the geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) parameter from EBSD of both the austenite and ferrite phases. The average values of dislocation density for ferrite and austenite decreased with increasing laser power from the value of $2.1 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2}$ for both phases in the SDM800 sample to the values of $4.9 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $5.3 \cdot 10^{-13}$ in the SDM1600 sample and $3.8 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $4.4 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ in the SDM2400 sample according to the GND parameter.

The chemical compositions of ferrite and austenite were very similar according to EDS analysis. Only the content of the ferrite-stabilizing element molybdenum was greater in ferrite than in austenite. Further partitioning of ferrite-forming and austenite-forming elements between ferrite and austenite did not occur, even with the largest laser beam size. The EDS results are provided in **Tab. 5**.

Tab. 5 Comparison of EDS results of ferrite and austenite deposited under different conditions.

Sample	Phase	Si	Mo	Cr	Mn	Ni	Fe
SDM800 [26]	Ferrite	0.4	3.7	27.3	0.9	6.3	61.4
	Austenite	0.5	3.2	27.6	0.8	6.3	61.6
SDM1600	Ferrite	0.4	3.7	27.0	0.8	6.4	61.8
	Austenite	0.4	3.1	27.3	0.7	6.4	62.1
SDM2400	Ferrite	0.4	4.0	27.1	0.7	6.4	61.4
	Austenite	0.4	3.2	27.4	0.8	6.5	61.7

3.2 Effect on tensile properties

The engineering stress–strain curves of the MTTs of the investigated specimens are shown in **Fig. 5**, and the results are presented in **Tab. 6**. Tensile test results revealed small variations among samples deposited under different deposition conditions in terms of yield strength, while the tensile strength increases with increasing laser power of

deposition. The sample of SDM1600 exhibited a higher value of elongation, indicating improved ductility, compared to other samples.

Fig. 5 Representative tensile engineering stress – strain diagrams for SDM800, SDM1600 and SDM2400 samples.

Tab. 6 Tensile properties of the deposited samples ($R_{p0.2}$ =yield strength, R_m =ultimate tensile strength, A_5 =total plastic elongation after fracture and A_g =reduction in area).

Sample	$R_{p0.2}$ (MPa)	R_m (MPa)	A_5 (%)	A_g (%)
SDM800 [26]	685 ± 11	812 ± 7	17 ± 1	9 ± 1
SDM1600	651 ± 13	849 ± 7	25 ± 1	15 ± 1
SDM2400	661 ± 12	884 ± 11	21 ± 3	12 ± 2

3.3 FEM results

The HTC used in all calculations was determined by comparing measured and calculated values. The HTC used in all calculations was determined by comparing measured and calculated values. **Fig. 6a** shows the temperature distribution for the $65\text{W/m}^2\text{K}$ HTC, where the measured and calculated temperatures are in good agreement. This coefficient was also used to calculate the free convection after the end of deposition. Therefore, the drop in calculated temperature for free convection after deposition is higher than in reality. **Fig. 6b** shows an example of the temperature distribution during deposition for the SDM1600 module. The figure shows the use of ATC, which combines several computational steps together.

a)

b)

Fig. 6 a) Comparison of measured and calculated values for $HTC=65W/m^2K$, b) An example of the temperature distribution during deposition for the SDM1600 module.

Fig. 7 a) shows the position of points P1-P3 where the temperature from the FEM models was calculated. The points are located on the axis of symmetry and are 0, 10 and 15 mm away from the platform. The temperature distribution at points P1-P3 for the SDM800, SDM1600 and SDM2400 modules are shown in **Fig. 7 b)**, **Fig. 7 c)** and **Fig. 7 d)** respectively.

a)

b)

Fig. 7 Position of individual points in the deposited block and temperature distribution at points P1, P2 and P3 a) SDM800, b) SDM1600 and c) SDM2400.

The temperatures are calculated as an average of several steps due to the use of ATC, therefore the maximum temperatures do not reach the melting temperature of the material. However, the mean temperature around which the calculated values oscillate will be close to the real value of the mean temperature.

4 Discussion

The use of a laser with a larger beam spot diameter and higher power led to a significant reduction in deposition time. The build rate increased almost fourfold when using the SDM1600 module (18.8 cm³/h) and more than fivefold when using the SDM2400 module (25.3 cm³/h) compared to the SDM800 module (4.8 cm³/h). On the other hand, a higher build rate results in the formation of a greater number of pores in the microstructure, which can imply a deterioration in the mechanical properties and the initiation of cracks during loading.

The microstructures of all deposited samples consist of a ferrite-austenite mixture. During the solidification of DSSs, ferrite forms from liquid (L) first, followed by the formation of austenite through solid-state reactions, as briefly described by the sequence $L \rightarrow L + \delta$ -ferrite (δ) $\rightarrow L + \delta + \gamma$ -austenite (γ) $\rightarrow \delta + \gamma$. The typical morphologies of austenite (GBA, WA and IGA) for microstructures of welded [29,42–44] and DED-ed [2,12,13,26] microstructures of DSSs are present in the microstructure of investigated samples. GBA forms at the δ/δ grain boundaries at the highest temperatures. WA grows from the δ/γ interface into ferrite grains. The lowest temperatures and the greatest undercooling are required for the formation of IGA within ferrite. Additionally, during multi-pass welding or subsequent heat treatments, secondary austenite (γ_2) can precipitate [43,44]. In the as-built state using the SDM800 module, the austenite content in the microstructure was 28 vol.%. This is a much greater content of austenite than that in samples prepared using powder bed methods, which typically have an austenite content of up to 1% in the as-built state [1,13,21,22]. On the other hand, another additive manufacturing method for preparing samples of duplex stainless steels via WAAM results in excessively high austenite contents (also exceeding 60 to 70%) in the microstructure in the as-built state [13,27,28]. The required microstructure consists of an equal proportion of austenite and ferrite, similar to that achieved after solution annealing [26]. In the as-built state, the austenite content

was increased by 20 vol.% when the SDM2400 module was used compared to the SDM800 module. Modules with a higher energy area density (*EAD*) promote the in-situ formation of austenite during deposition. The *EAD* parameter was calculated using the equation Eq. (1) [45], where *P*, *D*, and *V* represent the laser power, beam diameter, and laser scanning speed, respectively. The *EAD* is a commonly calculated parameter for DED in the literature.

$$EAD = \frac{P}{D \cdot V} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

In **Tab. 7**, the austenite contents in the as-built microstructures are compared based on the energy density parameters of *EAD*. Considering the laser power, laser beam diameter, and powder feed rate, the austenite content in the microstructure after deposition increased with decreasing energy area density expressed, as indicated by the *EAD* results in this work. Additionally, considering the results of other studies summarized in **Tab. 7**, the dependence of the amount of the in situ-formed austenite on DED and the DED conditions, as determined by the parameter *EAD*, was not clear. The parameter EW (calculated according to Eq. (2)) was introduced to include the powder feed rate in the influence on the amount of austenite in the microstructure. However, there is also no sufficient correlation between the parameter and the austenite content, as indicated **Tab. 7**. The in-situ formation of austenite during the DED process is influenced by numerous direct deposition parameters, but the platform on which direct deposition occurs and the heat dissipation rate also play a crucial role. In particular, the cooling rate will probably be key to the austenite-to-ferrite ratio in the microstructure, and it holds that a lower cooling rate provides more time at high temperatures and promote the formation of austenite. This statement is also mentioned as the reason for the increasing content of austenite with the increasing height of the deposited sample [12,37,38].

$$EW = \frac{P}{D \cdot V \cdot F} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Tab. 7 Influence of DLD-deposition conditions on the austenite content in the as-built state.

References	Laser power (<i>P</i>) (W)	Laser scanning speed (<i>V</i>) (mm/min)	Beam diameter (<i>D</i>) (mm)	Powder feed rate (<i>F</i>) (g/min)	<i>EAD</i> (J/mm ²)	EW (10 ¹¹ ·s ⁻¹)	Austenite content (%)
This work	500	849	0.8	3.5	44	7.6	28
	950	849	1.6	5.6	42	4.5	40
	1300	849	2.4	10	38	2.3	48
[2]	900	400	1.5	2.5	90	21.6	56
[12]	2000	636	4	15	47	1.9	58
[13]	1500	300	3	0.8	100	75.0	51
	1500	300	4	1.5	75	30.0	43
	1500	600	3	0.8	50	37.5	49
	1500	600	4	1.5	38	15.0	45
[37]	250	2000	0.338	7.1	22	1.9	45
	225	2000	0.338	7.1	20	1.7	40
[38]	2300	2496	2	16	28	1.0	33-54

In the literature, it is reported that a high cooling rate (10⁵-10⁶ K/s) promoted a very low austenite fraction in the as-built microstructure for powder bed methods [13,31,32]. In contrast, lower cooling rates (10²-10³ K/s) have been observed for DED methods [13,33–36]. We hypothesize that in addition to the cooling rate, the temperature

of the deposited block is also a very important parameter of DED process. Therefore, thermocouple measurements were taken at various points on the platform, and a numerical simulation of the temperature at the centre of deposited samples was performed. The temperature of the sample naturally rises and falls due to heating by the laser during the deposition of additional layers of material. These high temperatures are reached only for a very short period of time. Temperature profiles simulated at three different points in the deposited block are shown in Fig. 7a, b and c. From the temperature profiles, it is evident that during deposition with the SDM2400 and SDM1600 modules, the temperature at the centre of the cube is higher. The temperature exceeded 600 °C multiple times for the SDM2400 module and 580 °C for the SDM1600 module, whereas for the SDM800 module, it remained lower, with peaks between 500 and 570 °C, except for the first cycle. Temperatures between 500°C and 600°C are crucial for the phase composition of the SAF2507 SDSS, as shown in the equilibrium phase diagram of SAF2507 steel from the JMatPro software in Fig. 8. The austenite fraction increases rapidly in the temperature range from 500 °C to 620 °C. Similarly, the austenite fraction in the individual samples increases with the temperature of the deposited sample. On the other hand, the σ -phase was not detected in the samples because the rate of its formation is limited due to kinetic aspects. However, its formation should be considered in the case of very long DED depositions.

The results of the numerical simulation correlate with the findings of other studies [12,37,38] that describe the influence of the height of the deposited sample on the amount of formed austenite. The images show that the temperature at positions P1, P2, and P3 increases. Similarly, it was found that the amount of in situ austenite increases with the height of the deposited block during deposition in [12,37,38].

Fig. 8 Equilibrium phase diagram for austenite, ferrite and sigma phases of SAF2507 SDSS.

According to the GOS parameter, the area fraction of recrystallized grains in the microstructure increases with increasing laser power. According to Zhang et al. [27], recrystallized grains (with lower GOS values) exhibit

greater resistance to pitting corrosion. Compared to [26], it is evident that SDM800+SA contains only slightly more austenite, and the proportion of recrystallized grains is almost the same as that in the SDM2400 sample.

It is interesting to investigate the character of the austenite grains in the specimen. Higher austenite content for higher deposition module power can be attributed to the temperature cycles reaching higher temperatures when a layer is covered by its successors. The austenite growth occurs mainly in the interior of the primary ferrite grains and the morphology of the austenite is distinctively acicular. The Austenite grains also visibly follow some crystallographic orientation relationship (OR) with the parent ferrite. Detailed EBSD map from interior of one primary ferrite grain was acquired (**Fig. 9a**). IPF colouring shows the ferrite matrix being one-coloured with acicular austenite grains in it. The pole figure of the map shows that the orientations of the austenite grains are distinctively grouped around the orientation of the parent ferrite grain (**Fig. 9c**). This grouping is identical with grouping following Kurdjumov-Sachs OR for a martensitic transformation (**Fig. 9b**). There is a difference in a position of a parent phase position in the pole figure, as the martensitic transformation is “austenite to ferrite”, and our current example is an inversion case “ferrite to austenite”. However, it still clearly demonstrates the OR driven character of austenite growth in the duplex steel.

a)

Fig. 9 a) Detailed EBSD map of the SDM1600 sample – interior of one of the ferrite grains with large amount of acicular austenite in it. b) simulated pole figure of a Kurdjumov Sachs orientation relationship between parent austenite (red dots) and the 24 orientation variants of ferrite lattice in a martensitic transformation. Copyright 2011 The Chinese Society for Metals. Published by Elsevier Ltd [46]. c) Pole figure from the EBSD map above showing parent ferrite in red and austenite in black. Note, that the encircled orientation variants grouping in the model of martensite corresponds to the grouping of actual EBSD data in case of the inverse “ferrite to austenite” transformation.

From the perspective of mechanical properties, there were no significant differences in yield strength among the samples. In comparison to those of the powder bed samples, the strengths are considerably lower, but this difference is attributed to the ferritic microstructure and high dislocation density in the as-built state [1,21,22]. After solution annealing of the samples prepared by the powder bed method and subsequent changes in the microstructure, the mechanical properties approach those of the samples prepared by the direct deposition method. In comparison with the results of other authors studying the mechanical properties of samples prepared by directed deposition methods, a slightly lower strength but greater elongation were measured in this work compared to [2,13] and both, yield strength and elongation, higher compared to [38]. When comparing the mechanical properties of DED-ed SDSS with forged SDSS steels (yield strength of 610-655 MPa, tensile strength of 860-882 MPa, elongation of at least 25% [2,10]) it is evident that the DED-ed samples achieve approximately similar yield strength and tensile strength values, but the elongation is generally lower (with exception of SDM1600 sample), likely due to pores and oxide inclusions in the microstructure of the DED-ed steels.

The strength contributions of DSS derive from three main factors: solid solution strengthening (σ^{SS}) in both ferrite and austenite, grain boundary strengthening (σ^{GS}) and a dislocation strengthening (σ^d). Simple modelling of yield strength is provided using the law of mixtures (Eq. (3) [47], where σ_{SDSS} = overall strength, f = volume fraction of phases and σ represents strength contributions from ferrite and austenite assuming linear summation (Eq. (4)) of individual strengthening contributions σ^{SS} , σ^{GS} and σ^d as in [2,26]. The solid solution strengthening contributions

were calculated according to empirical equations as shown Eq. (5) for ferrite and Eq. (6) for austenite [48], while the suppression of the partitioning of elements in the as-built state was assumed and chemical composition of ferrite and austenite was adopted from **Tab. 1** for C and N and from EDS results for other elements in **Tab. 5**. The strengthening contribution due to grain boundaries was estimated based on the Hall-Petch equation (Eq. (7))[49], where $k_y = \text{constant}$ represents the potency of grain boundary strengthening and $d = \text{average grain size}$ determined by EBSD in **Tab. 4**. A rough estimation of dislocation strengthening contribution was calculated according to Taylor equation (Eq. (8)) [50], where $\alpha = \text{dislocation obstacle efficiency coefficient}$, $M = \text{Taylor factor}$, $G = \text{shear modulus}$, $b = \text{Burgers vector}$, and ρ is dislocation density estimated as geometrically necessary dislocation density (GND) parameter from EBSD. All the material's constants are listed in **Tab. 8**. Approximately the same volume fraction of silicon oxide as in [26] was observed in all samples deposited in this study resulted in a 40 MPa strengthening contribution from silicon oxide.

$$\sigma_{SDSS} = f_\alpha \sigma_\alpha + (1 - f_\alpha) \sigma_\gamma \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

$$\sigma = \sigma^{SS} + \sigma^{GS} + \sigma^\rho \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

$$\sigma_\alpha^{SS} = 1103.45C + 1103.45N + 25.8Si + 19.2Ni + 16.9Mn + 15.9Mo + 2.6Cr \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

$$\sigma_\gamma^{SS} = (1103.45C + 1103.45N + 25.8Si + 19.2Ni + 16.9Mn + 15.9Mo + 2.6Cr)^{2/3} \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

$$\sigma^{GS} = k_y d^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

$$\sigma^\rho = \alpha M G b \sqrt{\rho} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

Tab. 8 Materials' constants used for calculation of strengthening contributions.

Parameter	Ferrite	Austenite
M	2.7 [2]	3.1 [51]
G	83 GPa [2]	81 GPa [2]
α	0.475 [52]	0.475 [52]
b	0.25 nm [2]	0.26 nm [51]
k_y	239 MPa $\mu\text{m}^{-0.5}$ [53]	954 MPa $\mu\text{m}^{-0.5}$ [53]

From the individual strengthening contributions listed in **Tab. 9**, it can be concluded that solid solution strengthening decreases with the increasing EAD, while grain boundary and dislocation strengthening contributions increase with increasing EAD. On the other hand, two opposing influences affect the mechanical properties. Firstly, the refinement of ferrite grains occurs with increasing EAD, while conversely, the ferrite content decreases with increasing EAD. Both of these changes in microstructure should contribute to improved elongation and ductility of the samples. However, with increasing energy density, porosity in the microstructure increases, which generally reduces elongation and plastic properties. Inclusions such as silicon oxide have the same effect, but their influence can be neglected because they are present in approximately the same amount in all samples. The oxide inclusions were also observed in other studies dealing with the SAF2507 SDSS deposited by DED [2,26,38].

Tab. 9 Calculated values of solid solution, grain boundaries and dislocation contributions to yield strength.

Type of contribution	SDM800	SDM1600	SDM2400
σ^{SS}	248 MPa	221 MPa	205 MPa
σ^{GS}	248 MPa	243 MPa	271 MPa
σ^p	245 MPa	202 MPa	184 MPa

5 Conclusions

In this work, SAF2507 duplex stainless steel powder was fabricated using directed energy deposition under different deposition conditions. Deposition parameters such as the laser power, laser beam spot diameter, powder feed rate and building rate were investigated, and the effects on the porosity, microstructure, phase composition and tensile properties were evaluated. The deposition parameters were expressed as the energy area density (EAD). The major conclusions are summarized below:

- 1) The use of a larger laser spot size, higher laser power and powder feed rate (lower energy area density) resulted in 66% and 78% reductions in deposition time, respectively, when the SDM1600 and SDM2400 modules are used compared to the SDM800 module.
- 2) The size of the molten pool increased significantly with the increasing energy density (EAD), and the porosity of the samples increased.
- 3) The in-situ formed austenite content increased with decreasing energy area density. Deposition with a lower energy area density results in a microstructure with a nearly equal ferrite-austenite ratio. Generally, the distribution of austenite in the microstructure is more uniform, while the use of higher EAD leads to the formation of microstructures with austenite-free areas. In contrast to solution annealing, energy density does not affect the chemical composition of austenite or ferrite. Both phases, austenite and ferrite, consistently have the same chemical composition in the as-built state. With decreasing energy area density, the grain size of austenite increases, and the grain size of ferrite decreases. Note that the occurrence of secondary phases of DSS is strongly undesirable, and no secondary phases were observed in this work.
- 4) Based on numerical simulations, it was found that the temperature of the deposited cube during the DED process has a crucial influence on the content of in-situ formed austenite. The temperature within the deposited block increased with decreasing EAD resulted in the increase in austenite content. The austenite in the interior of ferrite grains grew in a defined orientation relationship to the parent ferrite, this relationship being determined as Kurdjumov -Sachs.
- 5) The effect of the deposition parameters on the yield strength was insignificant and all samples reached similar strength as forged SAF2507 SDSS. It can be concluded that additively manufactured samples by DED methods have lower elongation than forged material, probably due to oxide inclusions in microstructure and porosity.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pavel Salvetr: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal Analysis, Writing - Original Draft; **Josef Hodek:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing - Original Draft; **Matouš Uhlík:** Investigation; **Pavel Novák:** Investigation; **Jaromír Dlouhý:** Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing; **Michal Brázda:** Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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